

The Role of Students' Independent Work in the Educational Process

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ABSTRACT

The task of foreign language teachers is not only to directly teach students, but also to organize their independent work, as a result of which bachelors can learn some strategies for mastering the language. While organizing the independent work of students in a foreign language, the teacher must create conditions most favorable for the development of the creative potential of learners, coordinate their activities, and help overcome possible difficulties. The article deals with the issues on analyzing the significance of students' independent work in the educational process.

Keywords: foreign language, language, independent work, learners, difficulties, educational process.

INTRODUCTION

The main task of organizing students' independent work is to create psychological and didactic conditions for the development of intellectual initiative and thinking in any form of class. The basic principle of organization should be to transfer all students to individual work, from the formal performance of certain tasks with the passive role of the student to cognitive activity with the formation of one's own opinion in solving a problem. The purpose of students' independent work is to teach the student to work meaningfully and independently, first with educational material, and then with scientific information, self-organization and self-discipline, in order to instill in the student the ability to constantly improve his skills in the future.

There are two main directions of organizing students' independent work in the educational process. The first is to increase the role of independent work in the lesson. The implementation of this path requires teachers to develop methods and forms of organizing classroom activities that can ensure the independence of students at a high level and improve the quality of personnel training.

The second is to increase the activity of students in all areas of independent work outside the classroom. Increasing the activity of students in extracurricular activities is associated with a number of difficulties. Firstly, it is the fact that most students and teachers are not professionally

and psychologically prepared. In addition, the existing information supply of the educational process is not enough for the effective organization of independent work.

DISCUSSIONS

The significant role in the organization of independent work belongs to the teacher, who must work with the student not "in general", but with his own personality, strengths and weaknesses, individual abilities and inclinations. The task of the teacher is to see and develop the best qualities of the student as a highly qualified professional in the future. Independent work is aimed at developing the individual abilities of students, at improving the quality of specialist training. Independent work should be systematic in nature, taking into account the specific features of language teaching in extracurricular time. The effective organization of independent work in a foreign language is currently considered as one of the most urgent tasks of teaching at a university. This is due to the fact that the implementation of various types of independent work contributes to a more effective mastery of the material, the growth of learning motivation, stimulates cognitive and professional interests, develops creative activity and initiative.

As we know, independent work of students is possible only if there is serious and stable motivation. The most powerful motivating factor is preparation for the next productive professional activity.

Consider the internal factors that help to activate independent work. Among them are the following:

1. The usefulness of the work done. If the student knows that the results of his work will be used in a lecture course, in a methodological guide, in a laboratory workshop, in the preparation of a publication, or in other ways, then the attitude towards completing the assignment will change significantly for the better. the quality of work will increase. At the same time, it is important to form the student psychologically, to show him how necessary the work is.

Another option for using a useful factor is the active use of work results in professional training. For example, if a student has received an assignment for a diploma (qualification) work in one of the minor courses, he can complete independent assignments in a number of humanitarian and socio-economic, natural sciences, and general professional cycles. subjects, which will then be included as sections in his thesis.

2. Participation of students in creative activities. This can be participation in research, development or methodological work carried out in a particular department.

3. An important motivational factor is intensive pedagogy. It includes the introduction of active methods into the educational process, first of all, game training based on innovative and organizational-active games. In such games, there is not only the acquisition of decision-making skills, but also the transition from one-sided known knowledge about the object to multi-sided knowledge, modeling it with the identification of leading contradictions. The first step in this approach is business or situational forms of learning, including those that use computers.

4. Participation in Olympiads in academic subjects, competitions in scientific research or practical work, etc.

5. Using motivational factors to control knowledge (summary grades, rating, tests, non-standard exam procedures). These factors, under certain conditions, can create a desire for competitiveness, which in itself is a strong motivational factor for student self-improvement.

6. Incentives (scholarships, bonuses, incentive points) for students' success in studies and creative activities and sanctions for poor studies. For example, you can give an increased mark for a work submitted before the due date, otherwise you can reduce it.

7. Individualization of tasks performed both in the lesson and outside of it, constantly updating them.

8. The motivating factor of strong educational work and first of all independent work is the personality of the teacher. A teacher can be a role model for a student as a professional and creative person. The teacher can and should help in opening the creative possibilities of the student, in determining the prospects of his internal growth.

9. Motivation for independent educational activities can be increased by using such a form of organizing the educational process as a cyclic training ("immersion method"). This method allows you to activate the study of the material, because shortening the interval between lessons in a certain subject requires constant attention to the content of the course and reduces the rate of forgetting. A variation of this type of training is many hours of hands-on training that covers several course topics and focuses on solving interrelated problems.

The main thing in the strategic direction of the organization of students' independent work at the university is not to optimize its specific types, but to create conditions for high activity, independence and responsibility of students in all types of classes in and outside the class.

The goal of students' independent work is their personal development in the process of acquiring new knowledge from various sources. Independent works include working with

textbooks, educational manuals, scientific works of classics of psychology, monographs, collections of scientific articles and scientific lectures, scientific articles in specialized psychological magazines, psychological materials in periodicals, fiction. Recently, working with electronic resources (Internet system, computer programs and information on electronic carriers) has taken a large place in independent work. Students' independent works include writing essays, comments.

Working with textbooks and study guides often takes the most time for a student.

In psychology, it is customary to call a textbook a book that contains all or almost all programmatic material in the subject. As a rule, textbooks are compiled by groups of authors, and the seal of textbooks is determined by relevant educational authorities.

The textbook does not claim to fully cover all the issues of the program and includes teaching material on the subject, while individual topics can be fully developed, other topics of the program are not considered at all.

Working with textbooks should also be systematic. It consists of three stages. At the first stage, the student gets acquainted with the textbook or study guide, pays attention to the names of the authors, comments, examines the content, examines the table of contents, diagrams, drawings, turns to the text that interests him.

In the second stage, the student carefully reads the textbook (manual) from the first page to the last page with mandatory notes on separate sheets (it is not recommended to make notes in the books). These symbols make it possible to distinguish between primary and secondary, important and unimportant, interesting and uninteresting, definitions and descriptions of events, as well as other criteria for distinguishing material. In this case, the source page and its name must be indicated in the note.

In the third stage, a summary of the book is made, based on the notes, the material is written verbatim or its meaning is explained, but always it is determined from which page of the source the extract is taken. This will help in the future in writing term papers, research papers, thesis writing to avoid plagiarism.

At the same time, it should be noted that psychology textbooks often do not take into account all theoretical approaches, and therefore, in order to have relatively systematic knowledge, it is necessary to study several textbooks and a sufficient number of textbooks on one subject.

Unfortunately, some students use textbooks and study guides in the following way, while preparing for seminars, tests or exams, they look for the content section of the book, the paragraph that, in their opinion, perfectly corresponds to the question. Such use of the textbook cannot be called learning it, and the knowledge gained in this way will not be systematic.

As we said above, independent work of students can be reproductive and productive. Reproductive independent work involves the work of students with methodological materials and manuals, in which the sequence of studying the material of the discipline "Foreign Language" is traced, in addition, students focus on the features of studying individual topics and sections. Students, organizing their independent work in a foreign language, perform routine tasks in an adaptive individual electronic workbook during extracurricular time. Bachelors also have to solve problems and perform routine interactive tasks online; perform tasks according to the model in order to consolidate theoretical knowledge, develop skills and abilities (reading, viewing, taking notes, listening, memorizing, memorizing, retelling; answering questions for self-testing; repetition of educational material, solving typical problems, building, etc.) [5].

Bachelor students who perform productive work should be able to analyze a problem situation and look for new information. Productive independent work of students requires them to be able to choose the means and methods for solving the tasks (compilation of various texts, educational research and project assignments, course projects). Such tasks aim students at developing their creative thinking skills, innovative methods for solving problems. Productive independent work of students is aimed more at the creative and research activities of bachelors. Students can, for example, be invited to prepare reports for presentation at regular scientific and practical conferences. The teacher, for his part, when organizing independent work of bachelors, can create thematic and interactive sites, develop interactive documents and multimedia visual aids in the discipline "Foreign Language". To control the independent work of students in a foreign language, teachers can develop forms for standard testing and questionnaires, create test tasks with a freely constructed answer. Of particular interest in self-study of a foreign language among students may be the holding of web conferences in the language being studied. Independent work of students can be effective if it is more productive and is distinguished by versatile and diverse areas.

CONCLUSION

Thus, we can say that the basis for the functioning of the system of independent work in a foreign language is a number of principles that determine the content, forms and direction of the pedagogical impact on the personality of the bachelor. These principles are, firstly, to ensure a close connection of extracurricular work in a foreign language with the living conditions and activities of students (for example, students studying at the department of "International Relations" should be aware of current events in the life of our country and abroad. Of particular importance may be meetings with people who use a foreign language in their professional activities). Secondly, we note that an important condition for higher communicative activity of students in their independent work is the opportunity to choose the most interesting and accessible type of activity: correspondence and online communication with foreign colleagues, reading books and articles in the language being studied, development of skills and abilities of oral speech in the classroom of a scientific circle, etc. Thirdly, not only a variety of activities, but also its content side is of great importance for stimulating communicative activity [1]. The use of relevant authentic materials, their cognitive value and entertaining cause the need for communication, increase its quality level.

In independent work, as well as in the classroom, students must consciously apply knowledge, skills and abilities, since the formation of interest in foreign language activities largely depends on the understanding of the content of the material used, the willingness to include it in speech activity. Organizing independent work of students in the discipline "Foreign Language", the teacher must skillfully combine collective, group and individual forms of work. These types of work must be closely linked with other core subjects so that students see the need to study various disciplines in a complex.

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